

**Impact of Social Media on Creative Libraries: with special reference to
Public Libraries in Sri Lanka**

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ABSTRACT

Social media is becoming a very popular part of the day-to-day life of the human being. In this virtual community, people can express their ideas, knowledge, and everything with others easily. As an essential part of day-to-day human lives, a library can achieve more benefits via social media. Social media gives vast opportunities for libraries and information centers. This research identified how libraries can become smart and creative when using social media and their impact on society. The major objectives of this research were to identify the functions of the public libraries' social media sites for sharing and discussing the information of the library, how the authenticity of information and library resources is being promoted, how they educate the people in different ways, and how far they are being updated. The sample consisted of 10 leading public libraries in Sri Lanka. Librarians and site developers were interviewed with structured questionnaires, while their social media sites were observed to collect data. Thereby, technological methods and new trends practiced by the librarians, user attractions and activities promoted in their social media sites, and the effectiveness of the sites for creating the image of the library were observed.

Keywords: Library, Information, Knowledge, Social Media